

Effect on rice of *H. sacchari* at various inoculum levels. ^a Niger State, Nigeria

Inoculum level (nematodes/plant)	Tiller no.	Panicle exertion (cm)
0	6.55 a	10.50 c
1,000	4.56 c	12.55 ab
5,000	4.25 c	13.28 a
10,000	5.09 b	11.63 bc

^a Mean separation by DMRT.

Fenwick can and incubated in petri dishes. Inocula were applied at 1,000, 5,000, and 10,000/plant. Steam-sterilized soil was the control treatment. The experiment was laid out in a completely randomized block design with four replications.

Both tillering and panicle exertion were affected significantly by increasing levels of *H. sacchari* (see table). Above the 5,000 inoculum level, nematode influence was less pronounced. This may be related to the self-regulatory property of *H. sacchari* populations under limited food supplies: some juveniles die while others undergo sex change into nonparasitic male forms. ■

Stress tolerance—adverse temperature

Promising cold-tolerant and high-yielding rice lines for Ndop Plain, Northwest Cameroon

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Rice in Cameroon grows over a broad range of climatic conditions, from a dry tropical climate with less than 800 mm rain in the north to a humid tropical climate with more than 2,000 mm rain in the northwest and west. At Ndop Plain (1,200 m above sea level) in the northwest, about 3,000 ha is planted to irrigated rice with a potential for 15,000 ha.

The rice crop is exposed to low temperature (13–20°C) and associated disease problems (sheath rot [ShR] and glume discoloration [G1D]). Low air and water temperatures, low light intensity, high relative humidity, and intermittent strong winds are yield constraints.

Agronomic studies have shown that changing the planting time is an alternative to escape low temperatures during critical late vegetative and early flowering phases. However, the present area is cultivated by more than 6,000 small farmers, with limited ability to adopt this practice.

Varieties that fit a longer range of planting times are needed. IR7167-33-2-3 was released in 1986 to replace Tainan 5. Its medium, bold, and fairly chalky grain type was an improvement over the short, bold, and chalky grains of Tainan 5. IR7167-33-2-3 and Tainan 5 yield an average 3.5 and 3.0 t/ha under farmers' management. The need is for suitable high-yielding varieties with long, slender, translucent grain.

Two advanced lines, TOX3344-TOC-3-4 (derived from TOX3117-18-1/ITA212) and TOX3145-TOC-34-2-3

(from ITA212/B2161C-MR-57-1-3-1), have been identified as promising. Their overall performance over 3 yr (1986–88) in on-station trials at Bamunka, Ndop Plain, was good. Grain yields averaged 6.3 and 5.8 t/ha (Table 1). In researcher-managed trials at Dschang (alt. 1,400 m) during 1988, TOX3344-TOC-34 and TOX3145-TOC-34-2-3 yielded 5.5 and 4.6 t/ha, respectively. Highest yields so far were 7.1 t/ha for TOX3344-TOC-34 and 6.3 t/ha for TOX3145-TOC-34-2-3.

TOX3145-T6C-34-2-3 and TOX3344-TOC-3-4 show greater tolerance for low temperature and greater resistance to ShR and G1D (Table 2). Panicle tip degeneration was more severe in IR7167-33-2-3 and Tainan 5; this is believed to cause direct yield losses.

TOX3344-TOC-3-4 and TOX3145-TOC-34-2-3 have long, slender, translucent grains and, when cooked, are flaky, a characteristic preferred by farmers and local consumers. Palatability tests in 1988 placed TOX3344-TOC-3-4 as best in cooking quality and taste. It is a candidate for release for general cultivation at Ndop Plain. ■

Table 1. Characteristics of promising varieties or advanced lines for irrigated conditions at Ndop Plain, Northwest Cameroon.

Cultivar	Grain type ^a	Plant height (cm)	Growth duration (d)	Yield ^b (t/ha)
TOX3344-TOC-3-4	L/S	90	120	6.3
TOX3145-TOC-34-2-3	L/S	83	120	5.8
IR7167-33-2-3 ^c	M/B	100	110	4.6
Tainan 5 ^c	S/B	95	111	3.8

^a L/S = long and slender, M/B = medium and bold, S/B = short and bold. ^b Yields averaged over 8 on-station trials 1986–88. ^c Currently recommended variety.

Table 2. Reaction of promising varieties or advanced lines to low temperature and associated diseases at Ndop Plain, Northwest Cameroon.

Cultivar	Low temperature ^a		Disease score ^a	
	Visual score 4 WT (0-9)	Panicle tip degeneration 2 WF (%)	ShR	G1D
TOX3344-3-4	3	5	1	1
TOX3145-TOC-34-2-3	3	5	3	3
IR7167-33-2-3 ^b	5	10	3/5	3
Tainan 5 ^b	1	20	3/5	5

^a WT = weeks after transplanting. WF = weeks after flowering. ^b Currently recommended varieties. Scored with the *Standard evaluation system for rice*.